

The Conception of God in the *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*

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Abstract: Raghunatha Siromani's *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa* stands as a monumental treatise in the Navya-Nyāya tradition, characterized by a rigorous re-examination of fundamental ontological categories (*padārthas*). Balancing scriptural testimony (*pramāṇa*) with independent logical reasoning (*yukti*), Raghunatha transcends sectarian boundaries, even adopting *Mīmāṃsā* concepts to refine the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika framework. A significant yet understudied aspect of this work is his philosophical treatment of the concept of God. While Raghunatha engages deeply with the nature and attributes of the Divine within his metaphysical structure, a systematic study of his theology in this specific text has remained absent. This research provides a comprehensive analysis of the dimensions and implications of the concept of God as articulated in the *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*. By synthesizing his dispersed arguments, the study elucidates Raghunatha's original theological reflections and their impact on the broader landscape of Navya-Nyāya thought.

Keywords: God, *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*, *Dravya*, Raghunatha, Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika.

Introduction: Sri Raghunatha Siromani, the most brilliant exponent of the new school of logic, independently examined the *padārthas* in his work *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*. On reviewing this text, it becomes clear that among the various categories discussed and established by earlier philosophers in the foundational texts of Nyāya and Vaiśeṣika philosophy, Raghunatha being a rational thinker accepted only those categories which he considered logically established. Again, those ancient categories whose acceptance, in Raghunatha's view, was supported more by counter-arguments than by favorable reasoning, he refuted even if they had been traditionally established and replaced them with his own independent conclusions. Although this work belongs to the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika tradition, it does not confine itself merely to the traditional categories accepted by that school. In certain instances, he did not hesitate in the least to accept categories approved by the *Mīmāṃsakas*, even when they were opposed to Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika doctrine. The treatise is grounded upon both scriptural testimony and reasoning. Therefore, we may describe the themes of this work as the concrete manifestation of Siromani's independent philosophical thought. Raghunatha Siromani was a mature thinker with complete confidence in his own intellectual capacity. Siromani's innovative views generated a new enthusiasm within the Navya-Nyāya tradition, and many leading logicians of the Navadvīpa community, following Raghunatha's example, continually made fresh discoveries and recorded new arguments on various subjects. In this way, *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa* may be regarded as Siromani's greatest work.

Objectives: Although *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa* by Raghunatha contains certain discussions on the concept of God, no comprehensive and systematic study devoted exclusively to this theme has yet been undertaken. Accordingly, the present work represents a sincere effort to examine and elucidate the various issues and dimensions of the concept of God as presented in the *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*.

Methodology: This research paper applies both analytical and descriptive methodologies. It is based on *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*, its two well-known commentaries by Sri Vishwanath Nyayapanchanan Bhattacharya and Sri Raghudeva Nyayalankara, as well as other works in Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika philosophy. This paper

uses endnotes for additional references. Book titles are presented in italics, and diacritical marks are used where necessary.

Concept of God in the *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*:

In *Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa*, Raghunatha Siromani said that:

Īśvarasya parimāṇavattve mānābhāvaḥ, dravyatvasya trutitvāderiva parimāṇasyāsā-dhakatvāt. Tsya caparimitāvṛttitvamasiddham.¹

This means that there is no evidence that God possesses dimensional extension, since being a substance does not establish that He has dimension any more than it would establish that He is an element. According to Raghunatha Siromani, God has no magnitude whatsoever; He is not the kind of entity to which size applies. In the earlier theory, every substance was understood to have some form of magnitude. Yet the only description of dimension found in the texts defines it as a property that leads us to make comparative judgments such as ‘this is larger than that’ or ‘this is longer than that.’ Thus, Raghunatha appears to be asserting that God is neither greater nor inferior to anything else, and that such comparisons are inappropriate in His case.

One might challenge this position. For instance, the *Kāthopaniṣad* contains the well-known statement:

Aṇoraṇīyān Mahato Mahīyān.²

which describes Brahman as ‘smaller than an atom, greater than the greatest, the Spirit abiding hidden in the secret heart of this creature; when a man is stripped of wishes and freed from sorrow, then he beholds the Spirit; purified from temperament he sees God in His glory.’ To describe something as having ‘unmeasurable non-residence’ implies that there is nowhere it can be found not to exist. Ramabhadra’s commentary indicates that this position is only a halfway point. He states that there is no proof that God is a substance at all.

This claim appears reasonable if we examine Kaṇāda’s characterization of substance in the *Vaiśeṣikasūtras*. A substance is that which possesses qualities and motion and serves as the inherential cause of other substances. Kaṇāda says in the *Vaiśeṣikasūtras*:

Kriyāguṇavat samavāyikāraṇamiti dravyalakṣaṇam.³

God, however, would seem not to undergo motion, since all things are said to move within Him. The idea that the material and the spiritual ultimately share a single foundation is central to much of Indian metaphysics, which begins from the Upanishadic equation of Brahman and Atman—the ultimate cosmic principle and the individual self.

By Raghunatha’s period, significant disagreement had emerged between the Naiyayikas and the Vedantins, the former advocating pluralistic realism and the latter defending monistic idealism. A Naiyayika seeking to minimize the number of distinct entities had to remain attentive to Vedantin critiques and avoid inadvertently collapsing all distinctions into a single unity. From what we have observed, Raghunatha advances further in this direction than most of his contemporaries were prepared to do. Still, his theory attributes consciousness only to space and time, not to all reality, as strict idealism would require. Raghunatha’s conception of God presents an omnipresent and omniscient container within which various entities exist—some conscious, others not.

Nyāya–Vaiśeṣika philosophers accepted eight qualities of God (Paramātmā). Among these eight categories, knowledge (jñāna), desire (icchā), and volition (prayatna/kṛti) are three special qualities; and number (samkhyā), magnitude (parimāṇa), distinctness (pṛthaktva), conjunction (saṁyoga), and disjunction (vibhāga) are five general qualities. The ancient philosophers held that since God does not exist in a limited substance, His magnitude must be established through an unlimited pervading cause. In response, Raghunatha argues that even if such an unlimited pervading cause is admitted, the possibility of deviation regarding magnitude still remains; therefore, magnitude cannot be established in God.

It may be expected that various scriptures refer to the greatness of God. But if greatness is not admitted in God, how can the term “great” be applied to Him? The reply is that when scriptures speak of the “Great Lord” or “Great God,” the word “great” does not denote measurable size. Rather, with reference to the eternal, conscious, supreme Self—superior to individual souls—the term is used in a figurative sense. In reality, the causes by which greatness would be established in God—such as substance, conjunction, and disjunction—do not exist in Him.

The renowned commentator Viswanatha Nyayapanchanana, in his commentary on Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa, stated:

Na ca ‘vedāhametaṁ puruṣaṁ mahānta’ mityādyāgamavirodha iti vācyam. Tatrotkarṣavattvena mahatpadaprayogāt mahānśabdo mahatsukhamitivat. Ata eva vā ‘anaṅvahasvamaḍīrgha’ miti śrūyate. Evaṁ īśvarasya saṁyogavibhāgavatve mānābhāvaḥ. Tathā ca dravyatvam api nāsti. Mṛdaṅgādeḥ śabda-samavāyitvaṁ darśitam eva. Tena gaganābhedanibandhanaṁ saṁyogādikam īśvarasyety api nāsti. Prayatnavadātmasaṁyogāt paramāṅvādīnāṁ karmeti tu manorathamātram. Adṛṣṭavīśeṣodbodhād eva sargādaṁ tādrśakarmasambhavāt. Tasyāsamavāyikāraṇa-virahenāpi kṣater abhāvāt. Tvayāpi tasyāvaśyābhyupeyatvāt. Nanu evaṁ jīvanāṁ saṁyogādi-mattve mānābhāvāt dravyatvam api na syāt.⁴

Therefore, it is unnecessary to admit magnitude in God. Conjunction and disjunction do not belong to Him, and actions are not produced through contact or inherence in Him as in ordinary cases. It may be asked: if contact and similar relations are not causes of cognition and other actions, then in the case of the individual soul also it would be unnecessary to admit conjunction and disjunction. Raghunatha himself, in many places, denied that conjunction of the self is the cause of the manifestation of knowledge.

The later Navya school replies that just as in the case of God substance, conjunction, and disjunction are not admitted, so also in the case of the individual self it is unnecessary to admit substance-hood, conjunction, or disjunction.

According to the Nyāya–Vaiśeṣika philosophers, the soul in living beings and in God is different. From dharma and adharma arise pleasure and pain. Dharma and adharma are unconscious principles; unless they are governed by a conscious being, the activities of living beings cannot result in pleasure or pain. Therefore, for the manifestation of the results of actions in living beings, the existence of a conscious entity distinct from the individual soul must be accepted. In Nyāya–Vaiśeṣika philosophy, that conscious entity is Paramātmā (the Supreme Self).

The Nyāya–Vaiśeṣika school is realist. They hold that effects are produced only when their causes are present. Before the production of an effect, three kinds of causes must necessarily be present—samavāyi (inherent cause), asamavāyi (non-inherent cause), and nimitta (efficient cause). For example, a pot is an effect. Be-

fore its production, clay, stick, wheel, thread, and the potter must be present as causes. Among these, clay is the inherent cause; the conjunction of clay particles is the non-inherent cause; and the potter, stick, and wheel are efficient causes. Although the potter is conscious, the other causes are inert. Without a conscious agent, no effect can arise merely through unconscious causes.

Since the individual soul cannot possess complete knowledge of atoms and their combinations, it cannot be the creator of the world. Therefore, the Nyāya–Vaiśeṣika school accepts God (Īśvara) as the efficient cause of creation. He is the maker and regulator of all created things.

A further question arises whether God is one or many. The Nyāya–Vaiśeṣika philosophers maintain that since creation, preservation, and dissolution are accomplished by one omniscient and omnipotent God, there is no need to accept many gods. If many gods were accepted as all-powerful and independent, differences of will would prevent coherent creation.

Scriptural statements such as ‘Dyāvābhūmī Janayan deva ekaḥ’⁵, ‘viśvasya kartā bhūvanasya goptā.’⁶ also support monotheism.

At the time of dissolution, the elements of earth, water, fire, and air remain in a quiescent state. The school is atomistic and holds that the material world is produced from atoms. At the beginning of creation, when the accumulated merits and demerits of living beings become operative, God initiates motion in the atoms in accordance with adṛṣṭa (unseen forces).

At dissolution, composite substances disintegrate, bodies are destroyed, and karmic forces remain latent. When creation begins again, karmic forces bear fruit under God’s direction. Thus, cycles of creation and dissolution continue repeatedly.

Another question arises: since worldly effects are produced by bodily agents, must not the creator also possess a body? The reply is that agency does not universally require a body. In deep sleep, a person has a body but manifests no agency. Thus, bodily existence is not an essential condition of agency.

Another renowned commentator, Raghudeva Nyayalankara, in his commentary on Padārthatattvanirūpaṇa, stated:

Na caivam sati upadarśitasparśanādiviṣayatvābhāvābhāvādivihetutākalpanam niryuktikamiti vācyam. Tāvatā kṣatyabhāvāt. Na cānyonyāśrayānopadarśitakārya-kāraṇa-bhāvakalpanam sambhavauktikam iti vācyam. Viṣayatāyā nityatvenot-pattāv anyonyāśrayābhāvāt. Paramānudvyaṇukānaṅgīkrṛṇām navyānām mate tu mahattva-kalpanaiva nāsti, āpattvabhāvāt. Tathā ca jīvātmanyapi mahattvāṅgīkāro niryuktika eveti nipuṇataramālocayāmaḥ. Nanu dravyatvena hetunā parimānavattvaṃ sādhyamityata āha — dravyatvasyeti. Aprayojakatvādityādiḥ.⁷

Thus, whether atoms or their conjunctions are considered, all causes ultimately function under the guidance of an omniscient being. A final question concerns God’s will. In living beings, will arises from desire based on knowledge of an object. But in God there is no unfulfilled desire. Therefore, His will is not motivated by personal need. Rather, when the accumulated karmas of living beings become operative, God creates and regulates the world out of justice and order, dispensing results according to karma. Some being’s experience happiness and others suffer; yet this is not due to divine partiality but to karmic law. Without suffering, detachment would not arise; without detachment, liberation would not be attained. According to Nyāya–Vaiśeṣika doctrine, what is the magnitude of God? If God were atomic, omnipresence would be contradicted. If of medium size, He would be lim-

ited. Therefore, the ancient philosophers accepted infinite magnitude. However, Raghunatha Siromani rejected this view. He argued that attributing any kind of magnitude to God is logically untenable. God's omnipresence is not spatial extension but universal relational presence without physical magnitude.

Endnotes

1. *Padarthatattvanirupana*, Ed. P.T.G.Y Sampathkumaracharyulu, Pg. No. – 37.
2. *Katha Upanishad*, Ed. Aravinda Ghose, Pg. No. – 14.
3. *Vaisheshika Darshan*, Ed. Amit Bhattacharyya, Pg. No. – 20.
4. *Padarthatattvanirupana*, Ed. P.T.G.Y Sampathkumaracharyulu, Pg. No. – 37.
5. *Rgveda* – 10.81.3 / *Yajurveda* - 17.20
6. *Muṇḍakopaniṣad* - 1.1.1
7. *Padarthatattvanirupana*, Ed. P.T.G.Y Sampathkumaracharyulu, Pg. No. – 40.

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